

FLEXIBLE AND EFFICIENT MANUFACTURING OF TAILORED CABIN INTERIOR PANELS FOR URBAN AIR MOBILITY APPLICATIONS

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Keywords: Automated Fibre Placement, Tailored Fibre Placement, Adaptive tooling, Lightweight design, Composite panels

ABSTRACT

Urban Air Mobility (UAM) faces demanding challenges on weight reduction, efficiency, and sustainability in electric vertical take-off and landing (eVTOL) aircrafts. This research presents and compares three ultra-lightweight composite panel manufacturing concepts, tailored for interior applications, using adaptive moulds and fibre placement technologies. The first concept is a selectively reinforced panel using Tailored Fibre Placement (TFP) with functional integration, achieving surface weights as low as 1.640 g/m². The second is a selectively reinforced sandwich panel, topology optimized and realized using TFP with towpregs, reducing weight further to 650 g/m². The third concept employs robotic near-net-shape Automated Fibre Placement (AFP) of bindered or prepreg tapes directly onto adaptive moulds. Although highly automated and capable of 3D deposition, this approach is currently limited to straight fibre paths and less suited for function integration. Comparative results show trade-offs between flexibility, automation, material efficiency, and design complexity. The integration of adaptive tooling and modular placement strategies opens new pathways for rapid, cost-effective, and sustainable production of composite panels. While this work focuses on aircraft cabin interiors, the presented methods demonstrate broader applicability for next-generation lightweight structures across the UAM sector and beyond.

1 INTRODUCTION

Recent technological developments in the field of electrical vertical take-off and landing (eVTOL) have contributed to further interest and innovations in the field of urban air mobility (UAM) [1]. Nevertheless, a number of challenges concerning the power-to-weight ratio and electrical efficiency must be overcome before eVTOLs can be realised. The overall weight reduction is an important factor as it results in lowered energy consumption or allows for batteries with higher capacities [2]. In addition, studies have shown that the utilisation phase is responsible for up to 99 % of emissions in aviation, and sustainability highly depends on the use of lightweight components [3].

This is where ultra-lightweight approaches become very attractive. The efficiency of composite materials can be improved by optimizing their orientation, taking full advantage of their anisotropic properties. Topology optimization aims to generate load optimized structures, often enabled by additive manufacturing approaches. Thanks to the high degree of design freedom, the material can be optimally distributed, resulting in an increased performance [4]. The use of composites for these structures offers the potential for further optimization of the performance and the lightweight character. The production of composite structures with oriented fibres is crucial for their realization. Automated Fibre Placement (AFP) [5] technologies offer great freedom for the manufacturing of these structures. The Dry Fibre Placement (DFP) is used in a process named Crosslayer [6]. It uses spread dry carbon fibre tows (FixedTows or tapes) that are fixed by the application of an auxiliary binder system [7]. They are placed linearly by activating the binder system, mostly by heating, and enabling adhesion to the tooling surface [8]. That way, load-optimized preform layups are automatically produced near-net-shape [6–9]. Another preform manufacturing approach is the Tailored Fibre Placement (TFP). This process uses embroidery

technology to place continuous fibres according to the load paths in a 2D plane [10]. Different fibres like carbon fibres (CF), glass fibres (GF), and natural fibres (NF) can be used. The dry fibres are stitched on an embroidery base material using a zig-zag stitch pattern. Thanks to the variable orientation of fibres, the resulting preforms can be highly optimized in terms of load-bearing ability and material efficiency. For the selective reinforcements, anisotropic topology optimization can be applied depending on the supporting material layout [11].

Especially cabin interior panels, which are non-structural, are predestined for implementing ultra-lightweight construction approaches. Nowadays, interior panels for commercial aircraft are made of sandwich panels, manufactured as a combination of honeycomb core and glass fibre reinforced plastic (GFRP) face sheets in closed press tools [12]. With standard surface weights higher than 2.000 g/m^2 [13], they have great potential for material savings in the final part and for reducing production waste by developing more efficient processes. As the established production process for sandwich panels is complex, expensive, time-consuming, and hardly automated [12,14], production costs can be significantly reduced by the automated, modular, and versatile manufacturing strategies presented in this research. To unfold the full potential of quickly customizable preforming processes, an adaptive mould is investigated. The surface of this mould can be manipulated to different shapes automatically, which can reduce investment costs, storage costs, and production times [15]. The flexibility gained by the combination of adaptive tooling and fibre placement processes can help reduce the gap between design and production, and enable the fabrication of complex geometries. Though showcasing the manufacturing abilities using the example of cabin interior panels, this paper aims to provide an insight on the versatile application possibilities enabled by variable axial fibre placement technologies in general, not only for UAM applications.

2 METHODS AND MATERIALS

This research aims to introduce and compare three manufacturing methods for tailoring UAM interior panels to achieve significant weight savings at the expense of rigidity. All methods include the use of adaptive moulds and are based on the AFP technologies which are presented next.

2.1 Adaptive tooling

Most samples were produced on the adaptive mould “Mini” from Adapa A/S (Aalborg, Denmark), which is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Adaptive mould Adapa "Mini"

The flexible membrane allows for the generation of double-curved continuous surfaces that can be transformed within minutes. It is controlled by 64 pistons in an 8×8 configuration. This results in an active area of $600 \text{ mm} \times 600 \text{ mm}$, and a maximum area of $850 \text{ mm} \times 850 \text{ mm}$. As a constraint, the minimum radius is 400 mm. It must be noted, that the “Mini” is the research mould from Adapa A/S, larger moulds are available in different sizes and can provide areas of up to $9.000 \text{ mm} \times 9.000 \text{ mm}$.

2.2 Tailored Fibre Placement

In this work, a TFP machine TCWM-102 from Tajima Industries Ltd. (Kasugai, Japan), as shown in Figure 2, is used. This twin-head machine has two continuous feeding devices installed and offers a maximum working area of $1.550 \text{ mm} \times 950 \text{ mm}$.

Figure 2: TFP embroidery machine Tajima TCWM-102

2.3 Dry Fibre Placement

The dry fiber tapes are produced from CF with a spreading machine from M&A Dieterle GmbH (Ottenbach, Germany) and can be processed with a Crosslayer placement head of the same company. Basically, the Crosslayer end effector actively feeds bindered or pre-impregnated tape material, activates the adhesive with an IR-lamp and presses it to the tool surface [6]. This is usually done on the Crosslayer portal machine with a working area of 2.000 mm × 1.000 mm. Both machines are presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Spreading machine for tape production and Crosslayer portal machine for DFP

2.4 Universal Robot UR20

Figure 4 a) displays the collaborative robot (cobot) Universal Robots UR20 from Teradyne Robotics GmbH (Munich, Germany) with a maximum payload of 20 kg. One major advantage of the cobot is, that it does not need any safety housing, so its application possibilities are very flexible. For robotic AFP, a modified Crosslayer tape placement end effector, shown in Figure 4 b), is mounted. This tool can be used to directly apply tapes to 2D- or 3D-shaped surfaces.

Figure 4: Robotic DFP: a) Cobot UR20; b) Crosslayer placement head

2.5 Materials

During the manufacturing experiments, CF rovings of different filament counts are used. A 12K CF roving Tenax™-E HTS40 F13 12K from Teijin Carbon Europe GmbH (Wuppertal, Germany) is used for towpreg production. For dry TFP processing, a 50K roving Sigrafil® C T50 from SGL Carbon SE

(Wiesbaden, Germany) is used. The 30K roving Pyrofil™ TRH50 30K from Mitsubishi Chemical Corporation (Tokyo, Japan) is used for the production of tapes for the DFP process.

The GF base material for embroidery is E-glass woven fabric HexForce 02116 1260 TF970 from Hexcel Corporation (Stamford, Connecticut, USA). It was purchased from Wela Handelsgesellschaft mbH (Geesthacht, Germany). It weighs 105 g/mm². As an alternative, NF base material flax fibre twill 2/2 fabric ampliTex™ 5040 from Bcomp Ltd. (Fribourg, Switzerland) with 300 g/m² is chosen.

As a core material, pressure stable polyester nonwoven Soric® XF 6 with a thickness of 6 mm is chosen. In addition to its core function, it can also serve as an infusion medium. The dry weight of Soric® XF 6 is 345 g/m², the infiltrated weight is 3.600 g/m². It is produced by Lantor B.V. (Veenendaal, Netherlands) and was purchased from Gaugler & Lutz GmbH & Co. KG (Aalen-Ebnat, Germany).

Two resin systems are used throughout the experiments. Both possess low viscosity and long pot life. For the towpreg production, EPIKOTE™ Resin MGS RIMR 135 is used in combination with EPIKURE™ Curing Agent MGS RIMH 137 from Hexion B.V. (Rotterdam, Netherlands). All other Infusions are done with Epoxy Resin L and Hardener GL2 from R&G Faserverbundwerkstoffe GmbH (Waldenbuch, Germany). Especially for optical applications, the high transparency of this resin is beneficial.

3 DESIGN AND MANUFACTURING CONCEPTS

This chapter presents and compares three distinct manufacturing concepts, each implemented in the form of ultra-lightweight panel prototypes, which are described in Chapter 4. All approaches are developed to be compatible with adaptive mould systems, supporting both, dry fibre placement followed by resin infusion, or prepreg-based processing routes. The concepts differ in their design philosophies, functional integration capabilities, and fibre placement strategies, yet all target significant weight reduction and high shape adaptability – key features for next-generation aerospace interior components, especially within Urban Air Mobility (UAM) applications.

3.1 Selectively Reinforced Panel

The first concept is a tailored ceiling panel with integrated functionality, following a design-driven and bionically inspired approach. Drawing inspiration from nature, in this case leaves, the panel design emphasizes load path efficiency and multifunctionality. The central design feature is the selective reinforcement of fibre paths, strategically placed to mimic natural vein structures for optimized mechanical performance. A distinguishing element of this panel is the integration of connection functions. By including loops at the distal ends of the fibre arms, simple mechanical attachment without additional hardware is enabled.

Furthermore, the base material is variable, supporting the use of different materials for focus on aesthetics, lightweight design or sustainability. The TFP reinforced base is stacked together with optional added layers onto the tool surface. The whole panel is then infiltrated using vacuum assisted resin infusion (VARI) or vacuum assisted process (VAP®). This concept is illustrated in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Process diagram of the manufacturing process for the selectively reinforced panel

3.2 Selectively Reinforced Sandwich Panel

The second concept adopts a methodical, performance-optimized approach focused on maximizing mechanical stiffness through sandwich panel construction. This concept relies on the well-established mechanical principle that panel height contributes significantly to bending stiffness, which is enhanced by employing a low-density core material and stiff top and bottom skins. Selective reinforcement is

applied only where structurally necessary, thereby reducing the overall fibre volume and optimizing material usage. The design process, illustrated in Figure 6, is driven by topology optimization, which informs the creation of a modified reinforcement grid, termed the “Opti-Grid”, that serves as the basis for TFP paths.

Figure 6: Design process of the "Opti-Grid", starting from solid reference model, going through topology optimization and resulting in an optimized fibre path

For the panel fabrication using TFP technology, it is necessary to use material with compatibility to the embroidery process. The core material must be stitchable, flexible, and capable of maintaining its height under needle load and under surface load. Experiments demonstrated high potential for the lightweight Soric® XF polyester core material. To avoid filling this porous core material with resin, an alternative to vacuum infusion is needed. At this point, pre-impregnated rovings, so-called towpregs, were chosen to be placed with TFP. Towpreg-based TFP offers a resin-contained process with minimal resin waste, making it well-suited for low-mass applications. A known downside of this approach is the contamination of embroidery equipment with pre-impregnated material, requiring periodic cleaning.

The embroidery-based process deposits fibres directly onto two substrates: One layer is placed directly onto the Soric® XF core material, the other is stitched onto a base layer of the glass fibre woven fabric. These preforms are subsequently stacked and shaped on the adaptive mould, followed by vacuum bagging and curing. Figure 7 illustrates the concept of this process, which eliminates the vacuum infusion step.

Figure 7: Process diagram of the manufacturing process for the selectively reinforced sandwich panel

3.3 Near-Net-Shape Robotic AFP Panel

The third manufacturing concept employs automated, robotic near-net-shape fibre placement of fibre tapes. This approach leverages an industrial robotic setup wherein spread fibre tapes are applied directly to the adaptive mould surface in their final geometry, avoiding intermediate draping or reshaping steps. The consistent-width bindered dry fibre tapes are prepared from carbon fibre rovings with the M&A Dieterle spreading unit. These are used either dry or pre-infiltrated within a Crosslayer placement head, that is guided precisely over the adaptive mould surface by an UR20 robotic arm. The placement head consists of a tape supply for a film spool and uses an infrared (IR) heating unit to activate the binder or resin on the tapes. Subsequently, a roller system presses the tape with defined force, controlled by the UR20 onto the tool surface. This approach is limited to linear fibre paths due to the nature of the spread tape material and the placement head, but enables highly repeatable and efficient processing. The direct 3D deposition onto the adaptive mould aims to eliminate common defects like wrinkles or bridging, often found in manually draped laminates. Using this process, either monolithic or sandwich design can be realised. For sandwich panels, a core is placed on the bottom reinforcement layer and then covered with the top reinforcement layer. Figure 8 gives an overview on the robotic AFP process with dry bindered tapes and with prepreg tapes.

Figure 8: Process diagram of the manufacturing process for the robotic AFP panel with bindered tapes or with prepreg tapes

4 RESULTS

The selectively reinforced panel and the selectively reinforced sandwich panel are evaluated on the basis of the production of panel prototypes. For the robotic AFP, the concept is assessed based on calculations. All three processes differ in their intended application, in their weight, and in their stiffness.

4.1 Selectively Reinforced Panel

The prototype for this manufacturing concept is a cabin interior ceiling panel with a length of 2.400 mm. For this prototype, the moulding area of the lab-scale Adapa "Mini" was too small. Therefore, a standard tooling made from Polyurethane (PU) was used. The TFP process and the resulting panel are presented in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Manufacturing of cabin interior ceiling panel prototype: a) TFP on NF base with CF;
b) front side of final NF panel prototype

The NF reinforced panel structure includes two layers of ampliTex™ 5040 woven flax fabric and weighs 2.700 g, which converts to 1.640 g/m². Connector functions were successfully integrated in this structure while creating an aesthetic bionically inspired panel. This concept showcases the potential of design-centric fibre placement to integrate functionality without compromising lightweight objectives.

4.2 Selectively Reinforced Sandwich Panel

This panel, sized 700 mm × 700 mm, was produced on the Adapa mould with a radius of 400 mm. Towpreg TFP was done with 12K CF roving, preimpregnated with epoxy resin system RIMR 135/ RIMH 137, on the GF base material and on the Soric® XF core. The needle and the fibre guide unit of the TFP machine had to be cleaned thoroughly after these works.

Figure 10: Manufacturing of selectively reinforced sandwich panel: a) TFP on core material with towpreg; b) panel prototype

The resulting prototype demonstrates excellent mass reduction at 320 g, which is equivalent to a surface weight of 650 g/m². This approach highlights how methodically placed fibres in a lightweight sandwich architecture can yield high mechanical efficiency with minimum material usage.

4.3 Near-Net-Shape Robotic AFP Panel (Concept)

The feasibility is proven for this third manufacturing approach. The DFP end effector was successfully implemented and tested in combination with UR20. First layups have been realized on the Adapa “Mini”, one of them shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11: DFP with UR20 on adaptive mould Adapa "Mini"

As no prototype panel was manufactured to date, the concept is evaluated on the basis of weight calculations for a 700 mm × 700 mm sized panel. For the DFP panel with subsequent vacuum infusion setup, the core material is fully filled with epoxy resin. Therefore, this material is the most robust, but also by far the heaviest. The final weight can be calculated with the following formula:

$$m_{panel} = m_{core} \times (w_{panel} \times l_{panel}) + m_{tape, infiltrated} \times l_{fibre\ path} \times n_{tape\ layers} \quad (1)$$

The surface weight of the infiltrated core material is $m_{core} = m_{core, infiltrated} = 3.600 \text{ g/m}^2$, the panel width is $w_{panel} = 0,7 \text{ m}$, and the panel length is $l_{panel} = 0,7 \text{ m}$. The weight of an infiltrated 30K tape is $m_{tape, infiltrated} = 3 \text{ g/m}$ and the totalled length of the fibre path for top and bottom layer is $l_{fibre\ path} = 18 \text{ m}$. For $n_{tape\ layers} = 1$, this results in a potential panel weight $m_{panel, DFP} = 1.818 \text{ g}$, or 3.710 g/m^2 . Therefore, the robotic DFP processing route is not very promising. This is why future research aims to include the

AFP of prepreg tapes. The goal is to combine non-infiltrated Soric® XF with 30K CF prepreg tape. For a 700 mm × 700 mm sized sandwich panel, the part weight is also calculated using equation (1). The same values as above are used here, only varying the weight of the core $m_{core} = m_{core, dry} = 345 \text{ g/m}^2$. This results in a potential panel weight $m_{panel} = 223 \text{ g}$, which is equivalent to 455 g/m^2 . Compared to the TFP sandwich panel, weight is mainly saved thanks to the renunciation of GF base material.

Although the near-net-shape robotic AFP obtains the highest automation potential, it is limited by a less flexible fibre architecture due to the restriction to straight-line paths. Therefore, this concept does not currently support function integration, like loops for the mounting of connectors. Nevertheless, this technique provides a high-throughput, robust solution for producing contoured interior panels with excellent material distribution and very low manual labour input.

4.4 Comparison

Each of the three approaches demonstrates a viable path toward highly efficient, lightweight, and application-specific composite panel manufacturing. The three approaches are compared in Table 1.

Feature/Concept	Selectively Reinforced Panel	Selectively Reinforced Sandwich Panel	Near-Net-Shape Robotic AFP Panel Concept
Fibre Placement Process	TFP	TFP	Robotic AFP
Fibre Material	Roving	Towpreg	Bindered Tape / Prepreg Tape
Fibre Placement Geometry	Variable Axial Design	Variable Axial Design	Straight Lines
Near-Net-Shape	2D	2D	3D
Compatible with Adaptive Moulds	Yes	Yes	Yes
Design Philosophy	Aesthetic & Functional	Stiffness Optimization	Process Efficiency
Functional Integration	Connectors	Connectors	Not Integrated
Process Automation	Medium	Medium	High
Areal Weight (g/m ²)	1.640	650	3.600* (infusion) 455* (prepreg) *calculated values

Table 1: Comparison of flexible manufacturing concepts

The selective panel emphasizes design and function, the sandwich panel highlights mechanical performance via structural optimization, and the robotic AFP concept provides industrial scalability with streamlined automation. The choice between them ultimately depends on the specific application context, performance priorities, and available production infrastructure.

5 CONCLUSIONS

This process study presented and compared three advanced manufacturing strategies for ultra-lightweight composite cabin interior panels, all leveraging variable axial fibre placement technologies in combination with adaptive tooling. The findings highlight the immense potential of tailored fibre architectures to significantly reduce component weight while enabling either structural optimization or functional integration.

The selectively reinforced panel demonstrated that variable axial fibre placement using TFP allows integration of secondary functionalities such as mechanical connectors without compromising aesthetics

or sustainability. The proposed multifunctional concept is particularly efficient in scenarios where design, functionality and material diversity are of the utmost importance.

The selectively reinforced sandwich panel emphasized performance-driven design, utilizing topology optimization to guide fibre placement for maximum stiffness-to-weight ratios. Through the use of stitchable cores and towpregs, this method eliminated vacuum infusion, achieving the lowest prototype areal weight (650 g/m²) while simplifying processing.

The robotic AFP concept, although still under development, highlighted the benefits of high automation and near-net-shape capability. While limited by its restriction to straight fibre paths, the use of dry or prepreg tapes in combination with adaptive moulding shows promise for future high-throughput manufacturing, especially with further refinement of resin handling and tool-path generation.

Overall, the study reveals that each concept offers unique advantages depending on the application focus – be it function, performance, or scalability. Adaptive moulds played a key enabling role in reducing tooling complexity, cost, and development time, demonstrating their compatibility with all presented processes.

Future research will explore mechanical characterization, long-term durability, and the integration of sensors or active components. Ultimately, these approaches support the growing need for sustainable, lightweight, and functionally integrated solutions not only in UAM but across all mobility sectors.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work is supported by the Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy as part of the LuFo VI-2 research project “KONKAV” (FKZ: 20K2105F).

Supported by:

on the basis of a decision
by the German Bundestag

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